

Uses of animal species in ethnomedicine among the people of Rawalakot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir

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SUMMARY

Surveys for documenting historically used animal species and accompanying cultural elements are common in ethno-zoology investigations. Documentation of traditional ethnomedicinal flora and fauna knowledge is important for conservation initiatives. The markets where traditional medicine sellers operate are important sales points for mammalian species. Conservation managers and policymakers require information on local and alien fauna and flora gained from such markets. The survey was done from February to December 2020. To obtain ethno-mammalogical data, questionnaires were used. One hundred and nine informants, including instructors, business owners, students, laborers, and army personnel, were chosen based on their understanding of animal species' cultural and medical characteristics. Each species' local name, medical usage, and cultural importance were gathered. During the inquiry, it was discovered that 17 different types of animals were employed to treat various ailments. Meat (n=7), (n=5), milk (n=4), egg (n=3), skin (n=1) and honey (n=1) for the treatment of Allergies, asthma, black cough, bones treatment, cardiovascular disease, cold, cough, diabetes, ears, egg yolk, eye disease, fever, growth of brain, heart disease, cancer, hepatitis, high blood pressure, inflammation, joint Pain, liver, low blood pressure, lungs, ointment, paralysis, skin diseases, stomach, strong bones, teeth, weakness and yellow fever.

Keywords: Ethnozooology, Mammals, Ethnomedicine, Ethnomammalogy

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INTRODUCTION

Traditional remedies based on animal products are extremely important to both rural and urban residents (Altaf, 2016; Altaf *et al.*, 2017; Altaf, 2018; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Altaf and Umair, 2020), and numerous species of animals are sold for medical purposes around the world (Khan *et al.*, 2020). Researches for observing historically used animal species and accompanying cultural elements are common in ethno-zoology investigations (Alves and Rosa, 2007; Alves *et al.*, 2007; Alves *et al.*, 2009). Documentation of traditional ethnomedicinal plant and animal knowledge is important for conservation initiatives. The marketplaces where folk therapy sellers operate are important sales points for mammalian fauna. Conservation managers and policymakers require information on local and alien fauna and flora gained from such

markets (Kang *et al.*, 2003; Whiting *et al.*, 2013). Though numerous wildlife have been documented to have therapeutic purposes in rural regions, nothing is known about ethnomedicinal uses of fauna in urban societies (Waldram *et al.*, 2000; Aikins, 2005; Smitherman *et al.*, 2005; Alves and Rosa, 2007; Alves *et al.*, 2007; Arshad *et al.*, 2014).

Given the growing demand for the protection and conservation of wild flora and fauna, as well as the high value that lot of animal species hold for folk therapy and medicine discovery in industries of pharmacy, there is vital requirement to judge the cultural, social, ecological, and public health inference related with wild animal utilize. There is information available regarding animal species utilized for therapeutic purposes as well as the socio-cultural perspectives associated with their use by Alves *et al.* (2007). Many types of wild animals are used in both conventional health care and pharmaceutical enterprises around the world to manufacture prospective medications. This necessitates the immediate implementation of conservation policies. Furthermore, it is critical to document cultural, social, ecological, and traditional knowledge on therapeutic uses connected with wild and farmed wildlife.

Since ancient times, various parts of animals have been used in the avoidance and treatment of human wellbeing conditions, and such therapies are known as animal therapy. Animal therapy has a long history and spread worldwide. It has been alleged that approximately 4,000 years ago, the Chinese utilized earthworms to heal ailments. The “Traditional Chinese Medicines” are utilized to cure a variety of ailments, have documented over “1500 animal species”. Around “15-20%” of Ayurvedic remedies are obtained from fauna, and over “500 species of invertebrates” are utilized to treat both common and difficult sickness in subcontinent (Adeola, 1992; Zhang and Wang, 1992; Oudhia, 1995; Unnikrishnan, 1998; Alves and Rosa, 2005; Costa-Neto, 2005b).

Ethnomedicinal information gathered from indigenous peoples contributes greatly to the identification of new resources for profitable use, primarily in the industry of pharmacy. Furthermore, the development of treatments is based on indigenous tribes' folklore information. As a result, documenting of indigenous people's traditional knowledge is critical, because the creation of modern drugs in recent years has been highly influenced by the loss of cultural and socioeconomic characteristics of local populations in worldwide (Fabricant and Farnsworth, 2001; Alves and Rosa, 2005; Costa-Neto, 2005a).

Many animal species are used in traditional health care and pharmaceutical sectors around the world to synthesize prospective medications. This necessitates the immediate implementation of conservation policies. Furthermore, it is critical to document cultural, social, ecological, and traditional knowledge on therapeutic uses connected with wild and farmed wildlife. In this perspective, the current study was undertaken to I collect and describe ethno-medicinal characteristics of indigenous mammalian species used by local communities in Azad Jammu and Kashmir.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Rawalakot is present along the border of India, and adjacent cities are Bagh, Kahuta, Rawalpindi and at "Latitude 33°51'32.18"N, "Longitude 73° 45'34.93"E, and "Elevation 5374 feet" (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The map of the Rawalakot (Ashraf *et al.*, 2012).

ASSESSMENT OF ETHNO-MAMMALOGY STUDY

Field survey was conducted during February 2020 to December 2020. Questionnaires were used to collect ethno-mammalogical data. One hundred and nine informants including teachers, businessman, students, labors, and army were chosen according to their awareness on cultural and medicinal aspects of fauna species. Information on local name, medicinal use and cultural significance of each species were gathered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data collected from male (69) and female (31) and all are muslims. Data collected from Govt. employers, Teachers, Students, Farmers, Shopkeepers and Traditional healers. Data collected from different people of the study area and Most of the laypeople are literate and while other very few are illiterate (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Respondents features.

Table 1: Folklore medicinal uses of animals among the people of Rawalakot.

Sr.	Common name	PU=MA	Diseases	Respondents number
1	<i>Bungarus caeruleus caeruleus</i> “Schneider, 1801” Common krait Kala sup	Fat=Topical	High blood pressure, heart disease, cancer	12
2	<i>Daboia russelii russelii</i> “Shaw and Nodder, 1797” Russell's chain viper Sap	Fat=Topical	High blood pressure, heart disease, cancer	12
3	<i>Laudakia agrorensis</i> “Stoliczka, 1872” Agor agama Sandaila	Fat=Topical	Joint Pain, ointment	5
4	<i>Varanus bengalensis</i> “Daudin, 1802” Bengal monitor Kehskarow	Fat=Topical	Joint Pain, ointment	5
5	<i>Naja oxiana</i> “Eichwald, 1837” Brown cobra Chajla sup	Skin=Topical	High blood pressure, heart disease, cancer	12
6	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i> “Linnaeus, 1758” Common quail Batair	Meat=Oral	Cold, paralysis, fever	7

7	<i>Columba livia</i> "Gmelin, 1789" Common Pigeon Jungli Kabotar	Meat=Oral	Paralysis, asthma	18
8	<i>Passer domesticus</i> "Linnaeus, 1758" House Sparrow Chiri	Meat and Egg=Oral	Paralysis	11
9	<i>Passer cinnamomeus</i> "Tessminck, 1836" Russet Sparrow Jungli Chiri	Meat=Oral	Paralysis	11
10	<i>Gallus gallus domesticus</i> "Linnaeus, 1758" Hen Murghi	Egg=Oral	Weakness, low blood pressure	17
11	<i>Anas platyrhynchos domesticus</i> "Linnaeus, 1758" Duck Batakh	Egg=Oral	Yellow fever, egg yolk, ointment	5
12	<i>Panthera pardus</i> "Linnaeus, 1758" Common Leopard Cheetah/tanduwa	Fat=Topical	Lungs, liver, fever, inflammation.	5
13	<i>Capra aegagrus hircus</i> "Linnaeus, 1758" Goat Bakri	Milk and Meat=Oral	For growth of brain, bones treatment	16
14	<i>Bos taurus</i> "Linnaeus, 1758" Cow Gay	Milk and Meat=Oral	Diabetes, black cough	16
15	<i>Camelus dromedaries</i> "Linnaeus, 1758" Camel Aunt	Milk=O	Skin diseases, allergies, hepatitis	4
16	<i>Bubalus bubalis</i> "Linnaeus, 1758" Buffalo Maj	Milk and Meat=Oral	Strong bones, teeth, cardiovascular disease	22
17	<i>Apis</i> spp. "Linnaeus, 1758" European honey bee Shahd Makhi	Honey=Oral	Cough, eye disease, ears, skin, stomach	13

During the research noted that 17 species of animals used for different diseases (Table 4.1). Meat (n=7), (n=5), milk (n=4), egg (n=3), skin (n=1) and honey (n=1) for the treatment of Allergies, asthma, black cough, bones treatment, cardiovascular disease, cold, cough, diabetes, ears, egg yolk, eye disease, fever, growth of brain, heart disease, cancer, hepatitis, high blood pressure, inflammation, joint Pain, liver, low blood pressure, lungs, ointment, paralysis, skin diseases, stomach, strong bones, teeth, weakness and yellow fever (Figure 3 and Table 1).

Meat of *Coturnix coturnix*, *Columba livia*, *Passer domesticus*, *Passer cinnamomeus*, *Capra aegagrus hircus*, is used to cure cold, paralysis, fever, asthma, growth of brain, bones treatment, diabetes, black cough. Meat is consist of “water”, “glycogen”, “lactic acid”, “sodium”, “lipids”, “nitrogenous and non-nitrogenous compounds”, “calcium”, “chlorine”, “iron”, “phosphorus”, “magnesium” as well as “potassium” (Keeton and Eddy, 2004; Hui, 2012). Composition of meat is different result of the effects of several “external” and “internal” factors such as food, fauna type, breed sex, and so on (Cheung and Mehta, 2015). “Beef”, “poultry”, “lamb”, “fish”, and “pork” are the most common meat sources worldwide. However, in a few nations, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions, camel meat is known as the principal source of fauna protein that equals, and in some cases exceeds, the commercial importance of other meats (Williams, 2007; Schönfeldt and Gibson, 2008; Abrhaley and Leta, 2018; Haidar and Bashir, 2021).

Milk of *Capra aegagrus hircus*, *Bos taurus*, *Camelus dromedaries* and *Bubalus bubalis* is used to treat growth of brain, bones treatment, diabetes, black cough, skin diseases, allergies, hepatitis, strong bones, teeth, cardiovascular disease. Wiley (2015) is noted that milk is the oldest food and most important for health (Spreer, 1998). Mammalian milk has of lactose, ash, fats, solids, proteins, and water.

Figure 3: Body parts of animals used in ethnomedicine.

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